

عصر حاضر میں نوجوان نسل کے معاشرتی مسائل اور ان کا حل اسلامی تہذیب کی روشنی میں

**SOCIAL ISSUES OF THE YOUTH IN PRESENT ERA
AND THEIR SOLUTION IN THE LIGHT OF
ISLAMIC CIVILIZATION**

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ABSTRACT

Society bounds individuals, belonging to various different ethnicities, cultures, religions and languages. Whereas, Civilization makes the life better including raising the consciousness and reform the society to make it more civilized. With respect to Islamic civilization, it focuses more on "Wahdat Fel Hayat" that means to construct a moral and spiritual laws of Islam for social well-being of the individuals. Owing to this, various verses of Islam preach Human Rights with equality and equity among masses regardless of their caste and race. The Islamic thoughts are centered on peace and stability and only make the one superior on the basis of "Taqwa'h".

In contemporary world, where the political turmoil including internal and external instability has become a challenge for states and individuals, simultaneously, Youth are facing various challenges including joblessness, depression, Lack of social interaction, societal pressure in marriage on the basis of caste, Lack of equality in getting learning and job Opportunities and rising immoralities.

The study is an attempt to understand the literal and academic connotation of the term Islamic Civilization and it's significant for building a progressive society. In the same context, the research has proposed some possible solutions for youth as crisis management approach.

Keywords: Islamic Civilization, Human Rights, Society, Social Issues, Equality.

کلیدی الفاظ: اسلامی تہذیب، انسانی حقوق، معاشرہ، معاشرتی مسائل، سماجی مسائل، مساوات۔

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